
THE ROLE OF MODERN MEDICINE PERCEPTION OF INSOMNIA AND HERBAL MEDICINE

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Abstract: Insomnia is a sleep disorder which severely affects patients mood, quality of life and social functioning, serves as a trigger or risk factor to a variety of diseases such as depression, cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, obesity and diabetes, and even increases the risk of suicide, and has become an increasingly widespread concern worldwide. Considerable research on insomnia has been conducted in modern medicine in recent years and encouraging results have been achieved in the fields of genetics and neurobiology. Unfortunately, however, the pathogenesis of insomnia remains elusive to modern medicine, and pharmacological treatment of insomnia has been regarded as conventional. However, in the course of treatment, pharmacological treatment itself is increasingly being questioned due to potential dependence and drug resistance and is now being replaced by cognitive behavior therapy as the first-line treatment. As an important component of complementary and alternative medicine, traditional modern medicine, especially non-pharmacological treatment methods such as acupuncture, is gaining increasing attention worldwide. In this article, we discuss the combination of traditional herbal medicine, acupuncture, and medicine to treat insomnia based on neurobiology in the context of modern medicine.

Keywords: acupuncture, genetics, heart-brain axis, herbal medicine, insomnia, neurobiology, sleep mechanism.

Introduction.

Insomnia is used to describe the experience of difficulty in sleeping. When people have sufficient time and a subjective desire to fall asleep but have difficulty falling asleep or have poor sleep quality and wake up easily, people who suffer from sleep disturbance have negative emotions and affect their normal work and life, which they describe as insomnia.[1] Insomnia can be acute, chronic, or intermittent, and is considered the most common sleep problem in related investigations[1] and can be associated with other diseases and sleep disorders. In the latest diagnostic

etiology, it is proposed that insomnia is not congenitally secondary to other diseases, but co morbid with other diseases, especially with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome and restless legs syndrome are highly co morbid.[2] However, this does not mean that insomnia is not secondary to other diseases, and when this happens, other diseases are successfully treated, and insomnia symptoms disappear.

In the medical literature, insomnia is often referred to simply as “insomnia, but in this article, it is always referred to as “insomnia to distinguish it from other disorders that cause insomnia symptoms. Insomnia can be chronic (onset > 3 months) or acute (onset $\leq$ 3 months), and in the literature it has been classified as “primary insomnia, “secondary insomnia, and other different types of chronic insomnia (e.g., Psychophysiological insomnia), but this perception is now outdated and anachronistic, and the academic community has replaced these old, outdated names with the more widely accepted “insomnia.”[3] Although insomnia can occur in healthy individuals and may even be common, it can still be diagnosed as a disorder.

1. The mechanism of sleep and wakefulness

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To understand insomnia, we first need to understand the basis of sleep; sleep and wakefulness are normal physiological states of the brain, and 2 processes, sleep-wake homeostasis and circadian rhythm, govern the sleep-wake cycle. Sleep can be consolidated when the 2 can be combined.[3] An interesting new idea is that the sleep-wake cycle embodies an organizing principle during which each process is independent, rather than assuming that sleep has a single function.[10] However, this does not deny that neuronal plasticity also occurs during wakefulness. Sleep and wakefulness may occur simultaneously in a nonintegrated manner in different neuronal populations of the brain, and the states of wakefulness and sleep have traditionally been considered to be strictly separated in time, with the brain either in a

sleep or a wakeful state. The assumption of a strict sequence of sleep-wake and a whole-brain or no-brain state has been continuously challenged in the last decade,[5] with studies proposing that sleep and even may be a fundamental property of small local neural networks. Thus, individual cerebral cortices may display sleep-like states that occur somewhat independent of other cortical sleep-like states. Intracerebral recordings in rodents and humans demonstrated the presence of both sleep and wake-like neuronal activity.[7] However, it should be noted that the concept of “local arousal islands” to explain the subjective arousal experience of sleep may be too simplistic.

Nevertheless, the concept of simultaneous arousal and sleep now seems to be worth investigating in depth, based on data-driven approaches showing that even patients with insomnia have more typical light sleep electroencephalogram (EEG) features than controls during deep sleep.[8]

Insomnia: A disorder of sleep homeostasis and regulation?

Brain circuits are primarily involved in the homeostatic components of circadian rhythm and sleep regulation. Although deviations in circadian rhythm and in vivo homeostatic regulation are likely to affect sleep quality, there is little evidence that insomnia is caused by circadian rhythm and in vivo homeostatic dysregulation. Regarding circadian rhythms of sleep regulation, only a few complaints of patients with insomnia are sleep complaints caused by attempts to start sleep at an inappropriate circadian phase.[10] Similarly, insomnia does not appear to be caused primarily by a deficiency in the functioning of the in vivo homeostatic component of sleep regulation, and homeostatic studies have assessed how sleep deprivation alters slow wave activity in the EEG during the subsequent resumption of sleep. Slow wave activity (SWA), which is considered a measure to assess cumulative sleep stress, increased during the baseline night in both patients with insomnia and controls, but to a lesser extent. Although some studies have shown an in vivo homeostasis deficit in insomnia,[8] other studies have not confirmed this.[9] All conclusions were based on studies and analyses that did not apply strict deprivation protocols regarding in vivo homeostatic sleep regulation.[10] This means that insomnia may or may not have altered SWA; therefore, this is not sufficient to draw any conclusions about the lack of homeostasis in vivo. Although adenosine has been considered a molecule that plays a key role in sleep homeostasis, with functional genetic variants in its regulation altering the duration and intensity of SWA, recent Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) have not shown major variants in genes involved in adenosine regulation. The “monoamine hypothesis” proposes a role for norepinephrine in depression, with studies and findings including norepinephrine deficiency, prolonged increases in norepinephrine activity, and altered sensitivity of downstream receptor

responses. However, the exact role of noradrenergic transmission remains a mystery.[2]

Combining acupuncture and herbal medicine for insomnia

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In modern traditional medicine, both acupuncture and modern herbal medicine are effective in the treatment of neuropsychiatric disorders, but physicians tend to treat insomnia not in a single treatment, but more often in a combined form, most often with acupuncture combined with Chinese herbal medicine. Professor Lin Xianming pointed out that in the treatment of insomnia, “acupuncture should be used to regulate the mind first, and prescription should be used to regulate the body.” The combination of the 2 can treat both the symptoms and root causes, complementing each other. Ma et al collected 108 patients with insomnia of the heart and spleen deficiency type and divided them into a control group and a treatment group; the treatment group used the combined treatment and the control group used only the tranquilizing acupuncture method. Patients’ sleep quality and PSQI and TCM symptom scores were lower in the treatment group, IL-6 and DA were lower in the treatment group than in the control group, and 5-HT and GABA were higher than in the control group, indicating that the efficacy of the treatment group was better than that of the control group. This combined treatment method was effective in improving patients sleep quality and treating insomnia. The treatment group received the combined treatment, and the control group was given eszopiclone tablets, and the treatment course was 16 weeks. The results showed that insomnia symptoms improved in both groups, and the TCM symptom, PSQI, and Hamilton Anxiety Inventory scores were lower in the treatment group than in the control group. Serum luteinizing hormone and follicle hormone levels decreased significantly, and estradiol levels increased in the treatment group, and the changes were more significant than those in the control group. The significant decrease in serum luteinizing hormone and follicle hormone levels and the significant increase in estradiol levels after combination treatment may be one of the mechanisms for the improvement of sleep-wake regulation by this combination treatment.

Conclusion

Intersection of TCM and modern medicine

Modern medicine, on the other hand, from anatomy and biomedicine, has always firmly regarded the function of the heart in medicine as a function of the brain. However, theories have not remained unchanged, and the development of the heart-brain axis theory and the study of brain-heart function interactions have provided meaningful insights for cardiology and neuroscience. With respect to biological signal processing, this interaction primarily involves the linear dynamics of the nerve and heartbeat, expressed through time and frequency-domain correlated features. However, the dynamics of the central and autonomic nervous systems exhibit nonlinear and multifractal behavior, and the extent to which this behavior affects brain-heart interactions is currently unknown. The conclusions show that significant physical and sympathetic changes, such as those induced by cold-pressure stimulation, have an impact on brain-heart function interactions beyond second-order statistics, thus extending to multi fractal dynamics. These results provide a platform for identifying novel neurologically targeted biomarkers. These studies increasingly suggest that both the heart and the brain may not be central to the body and that there may be a possibility of a binary “heart-brain” central framework.

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